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MAKTABGACHA
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TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

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2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE TRANSVERSAL-METHODICAL COMPETENCE OF A PRESCHOOL EDUCATOR IS THE FOUNDATION OF EFFECTIVE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the significance of the transversal-methodical competence of preschool educators in the educational and upbringing process, as well as in the context of preparing future educators for professional activity in higher education. The quality of education largely depends on the mastery and professionalism of educators who possess transversal-methodical competence.

The "new format educator" of the 21st century is interpreted as an education specialist who understands the necessity of innovation, acquires or masters the required knowledge, and is capable of professionally participating in the process of implementing innovations based on this knowledge. Such an educator performs professional activities in a psychologically motivated and high-quality manner, understands methods for assessing learning and ensuring educational quality, and effectively defines goals, content, and conditions that contribute to the formation of a mature, successful individual with high professional achievements.

Key words: professional competence, educators, transversal-methodical competence, highly qualified specialists, professional-activity approach, and quality of higher education, innovative technologies, and professional development.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachisining transversal-metodik kompetentligining ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonidagi ahamiyati, shuningdek, oliy ta'lim tizimida bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayoni kontekstida tahlil qilinadi. Ta'lim sifati, eng avvalo, transversal-metodik kompetensiyaga ega bo'lgan tarbiyachilarning kasbiy mahoratiga bog'liqdir.

XXI asrning "yangi formatdagi tarbiyachisi" yangiliklarning zarurligini anglay oladigan, zarur bilimlarni egallaydigan yoki o'zlashtiradigan hamda ushbu bilimlar asosida innovatsiyalarni joriy etish jarayonida faol kasbiy ishtirok eta oladigan ta'lim sohasi mutaxassisi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Bunday tarbiyachi o'z kasbiy faoliyatini psixologik jihatdan motivatsiyalangan holda va sifatli tarzda amalga oshiradi, ta'limni baholash hamda ta'lim sifati ta'minotining zamonaviy metodlarini biladi. Shuningdek, u maqsad, mazmun va sharoitlarni to'g'ri belgilab, yetuk, muvaffaqiyatli va yuqori kasbiy yutuqlarga ega shaxsni shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kasbiy kompetensiya, tarbiyachilar, transversal-metodik kompetensiya, yuqori malakali mutaxassislar, kasbiy-faoliyatga asoslangan yondashuv, oliy ta'lim sifati, innovatsion texnologiyalar, kasbiy rivojlanish.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается значение трансверсально-методической компетентности воспитателя дошкольного образования в процессе обучения и воспитания, а также в условиях подготовки будущих воспитателей к профессиональной деятельности в системе высшего образования. Качество образования во многом зависит от мастерства воспитателей, обладающих трансверсально-методической компетентностью.

"Воспитатель нового формата" XXI века трактуется как специалист в сфере образования, осознающий необходимость нововведений, овладевающий необходимыми знаниями и способный профессионально участвовать в процессе внедрения инноваций на основе этих знаний. Такой воспитатель осуществляет свою профессиональную деятельность психологически мотивированно и качественно, понимает методы оценки обучения и обеспечения качества образования, а также грамотно определяет цели, содержание и условия, способствующие формированию зрелой, успешной личности с высокими профессиональными достижениями.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная компетентность, воспитатели, трансверсально-методическая компетентность, высококвалифицированные специалисты, профессионально-деятельностный подход, качество высшего образования, инновационные технологии, профессиональное развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In global educational and research centers, scientific studies are being conducted to improve technologies for developing transversal-methodical competence. These efforts focus on providing the preschool education system with qualified specialists, actively applying innovative methods and technologies for the continuous development of professional skills, and ensuring that future educators acquire deep knowledge and practical abilities in their field. In the preschool education system, the effectiveness of the educational process is enhanced through the continuous professional development of personnel, the use of modern educational technologies, the implementation of innovative approaches, and the application of a competency-based approach in working with children. Increasing attention is being devoted to conducting research in innovative directions within educational processes and to effectively implementing modern teaching methods.

In recent years, our country has established regulatory foundations aimed at attracting students to high-quality education, creating a methodological environment necessary for their professional development, and strengthening the participation of highly qualified pedagogical staff in developing preschool education in accordance with international standards. One of the priority tasks has been defined as: "Enhancing the status of pedagogical personnel, aligning their knowledge and qualifications with international standards, advancing the preschool education system through an improved structure of professional training and skill development for employees, and improving preschool education and upbringing processes based on scientifically grounded approaches." As a result, by improving the theoretical and methodological aspects of transversal-methodical competence in higher education, the pedagogical possibilities for developing the methodological foundations of professional competence in future educators are being expanded.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In M. R. Sobirova's research titled "21st Century Competencies (4Cs) in Blended Learning," it is emphasized that blended learning helps students develop the knowledge and skills necessary for mastering the four core competencies (4Cs): communication, collaboration, critical thinking and creativity. According to the study, possessing these qualities enables students to work collaboratively – to answer questions as a team, develop solutions to problems, and take responsibility for completing tasks while respecting their teammates ^[1]. Based on international experience, the implementation of advanced higher education standards and the design of educational programs are grounded in the competence model of specialists. Competencies in higher education standards are divided into two groups: subject-specific (professional) competencies, which define the profile of the educational program and the qualification of graduates, and general (core) competencies, which encompass universal human qualities. When designing educational programs, it is essential to maintain a balance between these competencies and to plan for the development of specific competencies accordingly. According to research conducted by international scholars and data from Bruxelles Formation, although transversal competencies have already been informally introduced into pedagogical practice, this aspect of education requires deliberate attention and reinforcement. This new pedagogical orientation enables a more precise response to the evolving organization of work and the competencies required – such as responsibility, initiative, autonomy, adaptability, resilience, and the ability to transfer skills ^[2].

M. N. Khushnazarova emphasizes that "in developing the professional competence of preschool educators, it is necessary to ensure self-directed professional development, maintain feedback and continuity, implement activity-based and learner-centered approaches, and systematize innovative and reflective technologies to strengthen educators' internal and external motivation toward their profession."^[3] In O. N. Mukhidova's research titled "Transversal Competencies of the Modern Teacher as a Guarantee of Quality Education," it is stressed that not only the ability to "think in a modern way" but also the capacity to gather knowledge from different scientific fields, integrate it, and effectively apply it to problem-solving is essential ^[4]. Transversal-methodical competence refers to the ability of future educators to effectively apply their theoretical and practical knowledge in professional activities. This research belongs to the category of core competencies, as transversal-methodical knowledge pertains to the cognitive domain and includes skills, while competencies relate to the practical application of knowledge and skills in real-life situations. Therefore, the preparation of future educators should not only focus on the methodology of teaching specific subjects but also aim to foster interdisciplinary interest as well as the acquisition and development of transversal and methodical competencies ^[5]. Competence plays a crucial role for students in realizing their potential – not only in education but also in personal and professional life, as well as in the increasingly globalized and unpredictable world in which they act as global citizens.

Today, innovations in preschool education require strengthening the independent and creative activity of educators and placing greater emphasis on non-traditional, interactive, and play-based teaching methods during educational and developmental processes. Independent assignments, problem-solving discussions,

and audiovisual teaching materials have a strong socializing effect on the professional and personal development of future educators. Through such pedagogical approaches, future preschool teachers are prepared for professional activity, their logical and critical thinking skills are developed, and their existing abilities are nurtured. This naturally involves pedagogical work that requires collaboration between educators and children, as well as among educators themselves. In modern conditions, the demands placed on future preschool teachers include not only professional knowledge and skills but also the ability to develop socially, personally, and professionally. Developing professional transversal-methodological competence in future educators is one of the key indicators of their readiness to become competitive and modern specialists. In particular, a learner-centered educational paradigm encourages future educators to develop self-improvement, self-discipline, and the ability to express their creative potential. The educational process in pedagogical higher education institutions enables future preschool teachers to acquire knowledge about humanity and society, history and culture, spirituality and enlightenment; to master foundational pedagogical principles; to engage in scientific and practical activities; and to develop pedagogical creativity and innovative approaches. At the same time, it ensures the right of future educators to continue their education and creative pedagogical activity ^[6].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The text presented by us clearly and systematically reflects the essence of the main scientific approaches recognized in modern pedagogy for developing the transversal-methodical competence of preschool educators. These approaches are briefly analyzed in our research as follows: Competence-based approach. The professional activity of an educator is based not only on theoretical knowledge but also on practical skills and competencies. The educator must act as a creative professional in real pedagogical situations. This approach focuses on developing problem-solving abilities, designing and analyzing the educational process, as well as fostering reflective and communicative culture. Professional training is evaluated according to the criteria of effectiveness, independence, and creativity. Activity-based approach. Knowledge is perceived as experience formed through the process of activity. It is implemented through practical sessions, reflective analyses, observation, task performance based on experimentation, and modeling of pedagogical situations. As a result, the educator becomes a specialist capable of analyzing their own activity and making innovative decisions.

Integrative approach. This approach ensures the interconnection of various disciplines, methodological directions, and types of competencies. Transversal competencies are developed at the intersection points of different subjects. It promotes the integration of pedagogical, psychological, and methodological knowledge, ensuring the unity of theory and practice. Consequently, it contributes to creating a holistic educational system and forming multifaceted, balanced competencies.

Innovative approach. This approach is based on the use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and interactive teaching methods. The efficiency of lessons increases through digital technologies, while interactive games and project-based methods are widely applied. Education becomes learner-centered, reflective, and creative in nature. Educators develop creativity, initiative, and adaptive thinking skills.^[7]

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The conducted theoretical and practical analyses show that in the current preschool education system, although most educators possess sufficient methodological knowledge, their ability to integrate this knowledge into practical activities – that is, to apply theoretical understanding in real pedagogical situations – remains insufficient. The analysis revealed the following key aspects ^[8]:

1. The professional training of educators mostly relies on traditional methods, which limits their ability to adapt to a rapidly changing educational environment.
2. Transversal competencies (such as critical thinking, communication, and creativity) are often formed spontaneously rather than through specific methodological programs.
3. The integrative approach in developing methodological competence is not sufficiently applied, resulting in weak interdisciplinary connections and limited holistic thinking.
4. The use of innovative technologies remains low, and the effectiveness of working with children through digital tools is not fully ensured.

Based on these findings, experimental work has demonstrated that implementing a technology aimed at developing transversal-methodical competence can lead to significant positive changes. During the experiment, educators actively participated through interactive methods, reflective analyses, project-based and practical sessions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the research process, it was found that the development of transversal-methodical competence: ensures the effectiveness of professional training based on a competence-based approach; strengthens the educator's practical experience through an activity-based approach. The integration of different components of the system is a complex and challenging task. Innovation represents the process of creating new and useful technologies from existing or newly acquired knowledge. The main goal of the new curriculum is to improve students' competencies in various subjects – especially in literacy and numeracy, which are essential for their future success. The paragraph also emphasizes how the use of bullet points, numbering, and formatting can help students organize their ideas and arguments in a clear and logical way. It further describes the methods and techniques that can be used to design and apply these features effectively in a text.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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